

Uncertainties and questions about the occurrence of *Cochylimorpha perfusana* (Guenée, 1845) and *Cochylimorpha callosana* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1856) in Hungary (Lepidoptera: Tortricidae)

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Abstract. This investigation examines the anomalous occurrence of *Cochylimorpha perfusana* (Guenée, 1845) and *Cochylimorpha callosana* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1856) in Hungary. It concludes the records of these species in Hungary are uncertain, and the presence of these species is questionable and unverifiable.

Keywords. *Cochylimorpha perfusana*, *Cochylimorpha callosana*, occurrence, revision, deletion from the Hungarian fauna.

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Introduction

According to Kovács et al. (2024), *Cochylimorpha perfusana* is widely distributed in mountainous areas of Europe (Alps, Carpathians and Pirin Mountains), *C. callosana* is widespread only in the north-western Balkan Peninsula and north-eastern Italy and local in eastern France, Corsica and Hungary. The other two members of the genus *Cochylimorpha* seem to be endemics *C. dorsimaculana* to Wachau and Retz in Lower Austria and *C. bucegiana* to the southern Carpathians in Romania. *Cochylimorpha perfusana* is recorded for the first time from Bulgaria; the first confirmed records of *C. callosana* from Slovenia and Hungary are given; in the north-eastern Italian fauna, *C. callosana* replaces *C. perfusana*. Records of *C. perfusana* from Ukraine, the Czech Republic, Slovenia and northwestern Italy require confirmation. The taxonomic status of the *perfusana/callosana* species pair and the occurrence of the species in Hungary are of particular importance from a Hungarian perspective.

Results

In Hungarian literature, members of the species pair have been evaluated in many ways. So, I will review the taxa chronologically from the end of the 19th century to the present.

In older literature, the Hungarian occurrence of *Cochylimorpha perfusana* was reported by Gozmány (1968, 1971) as *callosana* HS. This species has been included in the nomenclature since the 2000s (Fazekas 2002; Szabóky et al. 2002; Pastorális 2007, 2011, 2012; Pastorális & Buschmann 2018), although no authentic *perfusana* specimens are available anywhere in Hungarian collections. Apart from the lists mentioned above, only Buschmann (2004) has so far published a list of specimens from the collection of the Mátra Museum; however, the specimens deposited there (Jászberény and Nagykáta Cseh-domb) were incorrectly identified. They were all specimens of very light-coloured *C. straminea* (rev. & det. Buschmann). Therefore, there was no evidence of the occurrence of this species in Hungary.

Two so-called "historical" specimens from Budapest are known to be in a Munich collection (see Fazekas 1994). The provenance of these specimens is completely uncertain. They likely came to Jámbory's collection in Budapest by exchange or purchase. Insect trade was intensive between Hungarian and German-speaking areas, especially before the Second World

War. Some authors did not take authentic labelling seriously. Thus, a specimen from a distant area might have found its way into a collection in Budapest. There the collector wrote the name Budapest on it. This is very misleading for non-Hungarian researchers because the name Budapest only indicates the location of the collection. Finding out how specimens of *Cochylimorpha perfusana* from the Jámbory collection in Budapest came to Munich will require thorough investigative work. Notably, the perfusion label suggests the specimens may have originated from the Heinrich Disque collection (see Figure 1). The original site of discovery is likely situated along the Croatian coast.

Zoltán Jámbory held a position as an official in the Hungarian Ministry of Defence in Budapest during this period, and his family were also renowned insect traders.

The specimens in question were observed and examined in Munich (Fazekas 1994); however, the anomalies above were not considered at that time. According to Fazekas (1994), this species occurs infrequently and in localised areas within Hungary. The morphologically highly variable *C. perfusana* exhibits sparse distribution across Europe, with its range characterised by a dispersed pattern. Variations in genital structure can be observed among populations from different localities. The taxonomic status of the Hungarian population remains unresolved. The wing pattern of the specimen from Budapest deviates from that documented in the literature (see Fig. 1).

The causal relationships of the previous identification anomalies can be derived from the following. It is necessary to reference the works of Razowski (Razowski 1970: p. 162, 2002, 2009), wherein the author erroneously credits "Herrich-Schäffer, 1851" with the description of *callosana*, and incorrectly states the type locality as "Niederösterreich: Schneeberg". These data pertain to *Cochylimorpha perfusana*. The correct year of Herrich-Schäffer's description of *Cochylimorpha callosana* is 1856, and the proper type locality is Fiume (= Rijeka), Croatia.

***Cochylimorpha perfusana* (Guenée, 1845)**

Argyrolepis perfusana Guenée, 1845, Annales de la Société entomologique de France. Deuxième Série 3: 302. Locus typicus: Austrian Alps and Dauphiné in France.

Cochylis perfusana Herrich-Schäffer 1851: 183.

Euxanthis perfusana Kennel 1913: 320, pl. 14 fig. 19.

Stenodes perfusana Razowski 1970: 162, colour pl. 8 fig. 79-1, pl. 59 fig. 79, pl. 127 fig. 79.

Cochylimorpha perfusana Razowski 1991: 105; 2001: 36, colour pl. 3 fig. 51; 2002: 43, colour pl. 5 fig. 91; 2009: 37, colour pl. 3 fig. 97.

Hungarian literary data: Gozmány 1968, 1971; Fazekas 1995; Buschmann 2004, 2022; Pastorális & Buschmann 2018.; Szabóky et al. 2002.

Fazekas (2022) deleted the species from the Hungarian species list: „*Cochylimorpha perfusana* (Guenée, 1845): The species *C. perfusana* was erroneously identified and published in Hungary (Buschmann 2004, Gozmány 1968, 1971, Pastorális & Buschmann 2018). No *C. perfusana* specimens have been found in collections so far. All specimens identified as *C. perfusana* belong to the species *Cochylimorpha straminea* (see Figs 11-12).”

Distribution. According to Kovács et al. (2024), *C. perfusana* is widespread in scattered localities in mountainous areas of Europe: Austria (Oberösterreich, Steiermark, Rax area), Romania (Bicaz Gorge), Switzerland (Bern, Chasseral), France (Hautes-Alpes: Le Monétier-les-Bains and Névache. More data from Razowski (1970, 2009); Ukraine (Crimea). Guenée (1845: 302) in the original species description mentions the entire Austrian Alps and Dauphiné in France as type localities. Staudinger and Wocke (1871: 242) mention the Austrian Alps and Serbia.

***Cochylimorpha callosana* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1856)**

Cochylis callosana Herrich-Schäffer, 1856, Systematische Bearbeitung der Schmetterlinge von Europa 6: 157. Type locality: Fiume, currently Rijeka in Croatia. Synonymized with *Stenodes perfusana* (Guenée, 1845) by Razowski (1970: 38).

Stenodes perfusana (Guen.) Razowski 1987: 250 figs 70–72, 313 figs 562–563.

Cochylimorpha perfusana (Guenée, 1845) Razowski 2001: 111 pl. 8 fig. 51, 186 pl. 83 fig. 51; 2002: pl. 10 fig. 91, pl. 47 fig. 91; 2009: 138 pl. 9 fig. 97, 169 pl. 40 fig. 97.

According to Kovács et al. (2024), the *C. callosana* is documented from Hungary: "Hungary: 1 ♂, 1 ♀, Budapest, Jambory [= Csillebérc], Sammlung [= collection] Disque". The subsequent

spelling appears to be a misinterpretation. Jambory is a personal name (refer to the introduction) and is not synonymous with "Chillebérc" (German: Dreihotter), which is a district of Budapest. It is a favoured location for excursions, and its environs were a frequent site for Budapest lepidopterists, particularly in the 19th and early 20th centuries.

Distribution. According to Kovács et al. (2024), *C. callosana* is prevalent in the north-western region of the Balkan Peninsula (Croatia and Slovenia) and north-eastern Italy, with localised presence in eastern France (Prémanon), and historical records from Corsica (France) and Hungary. The type locality is Rijeka (formerly Fiume) in north-western Croatia (Herrich-Schäffer 1856: 157). Razowski (1970: 162; 2002: 43; 2009: 37) erroneously cites Lower Austria: Schneeberg or solely Austria as the type locality of the species; however, these records pertain to *C. perfusana* (Herrich-Schäffer 1851: 183). The reported occurrence in Hungary should be disregarded.

Summary. 9 species of *Cochylimorpha* have been confirmed to occur in Hungary based on the studies and collection revisions carried out so far (Fazekas 2022):

- Cochylimorpha hilarana* (Herrich-Schäffer, [1815])
- Cochylimorpha halophilana* (Christoph, 1872)
- Cochylimorpha elongana* (Fischer von Röslerstamm, 1839)
- Cochylimorpha subwoliniana* (Danilevsky, 1962)
- Cochylimorpha woliniana* (Schleich, 1868)
- Cochylimorpha obliquana* (Eversmann, 1844)
- Cochylimorpha jucundana* (Treitschke, 1835)
- Cochylimorpha straminea* (Haworth, 1811)
- Cochylimorpha alternana* (Curtis, 1831)

Table 1. Flight periods and larval foodplants.

The following table gives the known Hungarian *Cochylimorpha* species (see Fazekas 2022)

Species	Flight period	Larval foodplants
1. <i>C. hilarana</i>	from July to August	<i>Artemisia campestris</i>
2. <i>C. halophilana</i>	from July to September	<i>Artemisia santonicum</i>
3. <i>C. elongana</i>	April-May and June-July	<i>Achillea millefolium</i> , <i>Artemisia campestris</i> , <i>A. vulgaris</i> , <i>Helichrysum arenarium</i>
4. <i>C. subwoliniana</i>	from the end of April to mid-July	The food plants and developmental stages of the larvae are still unknown.
5. <i>C. woliniana</i>	from July to August	<i>Artemisia absinthium</i>
6. <i>C. obliquana</i>	from May to June and July to September	<i>Artemisia maritima</i> , <i>A. santonicum</i>
7. <i>C. jucundana</i>	from June to August	probably a species of <i>Artemisia</i> (There are no valid studies in Hungary)
8. <i>C. straminea</i>	from May to July and August to September	They live on species of <i>Artemisia</i> , <i>Centaurea</i> , <i>Chrysanthemum</i> and <i>Scabiosa</i>
9. <i>C. alternana</i>	from April to June and July to September	They live in the flower heads of <i>Centaurea scabiosa</i>

Fig. 1. Wing pattern and original label of *Cochylimorpha perfusana* (see text for details)

Fig. 2. Distribution of *Cochylimorpha perfusana* in Europe. ----- line hypothetical area centre. ● fragments of a postglacially larger range

Fig. 3. Wing pattern and original label of *Cochylimorpha callosana* (see text for details) [After Kovács et al. 2024]

Fig. 4. Distribution of *Cochylimorpha callosana* in Europe. - - - - - line hypothetical area centre. ● fragments of a postglacially larger range

Based on the available evidence, it can be concluded that *Cochylimorpha perfusana* (Guenée, 1845) and *Cochylimorpha callosana* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1856) are not present in the Hungarian fauna. All previous reports of their occurrence are based on erroneous information.

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